

WAYS TO EXPAND NETWORK MARKETING AND E-COMMERCE IN THE WHOLESALE TRADE OF MEDICINES

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Abstract. *This article examines how more pharmaceutical organizations are using social media sites or e-commerce sites as digital marketing platforms to enable customers to get information and order pharmaceutical products or purchase products online.*

Keywords: *pharmaceutical industry products, commercial sites, advertising, enterprise, customer.*

In the 2022-2026 development strategy of our country, approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of "increasing the production volume of pharmaceutical industry products by 3 times and increasing the level of supply to the local market to 80%" confirms the importance of this sector for the well-being of our people. In this situation, the improvement of marketing activities of pharmaceutical enterprises occupies a great place.

For effective advertising, it is recommended to use several channels at the same time:

Create an official website and develop its concept. Landing pages are suitable for promoting a specific product (biological supplements, drugs, vitamin complexes) - one-page sites. On the site, you can highlight the main advantages of the drug / manufacturer, show the composition, post reviews, leave a feedback form with customers.

Development of special projects. Close medical blogs, channels on video hosting sites, publications on third-party resources work well in this area. For example, to sell immunomodulators, you can create a collection of articles on strengthening the immune system, where you can encourage people to buy the advertised product.

Development of social networks. Major pharmaceutical companies have long maintained Instagram pages, Facebook communities, and YouTube channels. With proper advertising, they convert well, increase brand awareness and gain loyal customers.

Advertising in mass media. Marketing departments of pharmaceutical corporations work closely with television channels and radio stations. A popular trend is the promotion of drugs by millionaire bloggers on social networks.

The main idea of customer analysis is to get maximum information about customers from internal data. The source of such information in the pharmacy network can be, in particular, receipts. And if the network has a loyalty program, you can have even more opportunities for analysis and answers to many questions. Thanks to the collected data, the number of network customers, their characteristics (gender, age, shopping frequency, average check, shopping relationship, basket width, check length, etc.), consumption patterns by regions and points of sale, as well as opportunities for targeted, relevant communication with customers.

A mutually beneficial cooperation between the network and the manufacturer on the exchange of information is possible. This is a big plus for the manufacturer, because a deep understanding of the characteristics of the end consumer allows for more accurate planning of advertising and promotional activities, as well as communication with the end consumer on behalf of the pharmacy chain.

Of course, all customers are different. Therefore, in order to better understand the consumer and his needs, segmentation is used, which allows you to divide customers into different groups. Segmentation can be done according to various criteria - gender, age, geographic factor, lifestyle, etc. ABC-, RFM-analysis (English Recency Frequency Monetary - recipe, frequency, money) is used for segmentation. Also, segmentation by life cycle stage is popular in Western markets.

The customer life cycle is a term that describes the stages in which a customer learns about a company's product, makes a purchase decision, pays, uses it, and becomes a loyal customer. In an ideal scenario, the value of the brand/company in the eyes of the customer increases over time and he becomes a loyal customer, but often the value changes over time: the value increases and then decreases. Dependence on the change of the customer's value over time, as a rule, is depicted graphically. This is the customer life cycle curve.

At different stages of the life cycle, customer communication strategies can be different:

New customers: welcome program for new customers, newsletters.

Known active, stable customers: birthday greetings, loyalty program offers.

Inactive customer (ceased to be active for 3 months): reactivation programs, research and offers.

A lost customer.

Of course, new customers will always appear, some will leave, and some will become a permanent core. How to understand how many customers are stable core and how many are regular customers? The "Leaky Bucket" model helps to determine this. This model assumes that customers are divided into several groups based on their life cycle stages. You can use names like "new", "stable", "churn", "random". Depending on the nature of the behavior in different periods, the customer falls into a certain segment. Thus, using the "leaky bucket" model allows us to understand the percentage of customer churn, how many new customers need to be attracted to cover the churn, etc.

It is desirable to understand the structure of the customer asset not only in terms of life cycle stage or socio-demographic characteristics. After all, someone comes to the pharmacy for medicine, someone for vitamins, someone for care or medical cosmetics, someone for children's goods.

Therefore, it is inappropriate to present the same offers to all customers. Instead, different offers and communication methods should be used for different groups of customers. Clustering tools can be used to separate such groups.

Clustering is the process of dividing a given sample of objects into subsets (usually non-overlapping) called clusters, so that each cluster consists of similar objects and objects from different clusters are significantly differs in degree.

What is the difference between segmentation and clustering? Segments are predefined, while clusters are not. Clusters require different interpretation than segments. In segmentation, the result is always predictable. On the other hand, clustering can be full of "surprises".

Clustering clearly defines the differences between customers, allowing to manage their heterogeneity. This tool will help you look at the customer structure in a completely new way and build relationships with consumers. The goal of clustering is to extract new knowledge from your data. It's like finding treasure in your basement.

Understanding customers and their needs allows you to create targeted offers. The use of clustering for the loyalty program helps, in particular, to formulate a strategy for working with

selected (priority) clusters, to develop a communication plan focusing on clusters, to calculate the economics of working with clusters, to model income and to obtain additional income. income, to develop cooperation

Digital marketing is a new stage in the development of pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan. Pharmaceutical and medical organizations are beginning to take advantage of technological innovations that allow patients to gain more information about their condition and control their health, while doctors are given the opportunity to quickly communicate with patients throughout the treatment process.

Some pharmaceutical companies are trying to understand the true value of digital technology, while others are already incorporating it into their broader marketing strategy. However, not all companies can sell pharmaceutical products online because they manufacture prescription drugs that cannot be sold this way. However, they use digital methods to communicate with healthcare providers and patients. For example, Pfizer actively and responsively responds to customer inquiries through social media, using YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter to communicate with customers. Johnson&Johnson was one of the first to launch its own dedicated YouTube channel. Currently, many large pharmaceutical companies have a global presence in social networks.

More and more pharmaceutical organizations are using social media sites or e-commerce sites as digital marketing platforms to enable customers to learn about and order pharmaceutical products or purchase products online.

Due to digitization and modern communication technologies, changes in the behavior patterns of society give consumers the opportunity to receive services and purchase goods through the use of online services. Promotion of drugs, medical devices, dietary supplements,

The use of pharmaceutical services, digital marketing tools and methods on the Internet is a promising direction for the development of pharmaceutical organizations.

Electronic devices connected to the Internet have become an integral part of modern life, which is serving to increase the number of online orders in all industries.

retail. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the period of self-isolation and restrictions on the movement of the population has shown the need to develop online services for consumers. A large number of patients apply to book medicines, vitamins, dietary supplements, which in turn is a driving mechanism for the development of digital marketing, sales in online pharmacies. Home delivery is relevant in the field of non-prescription drugs, as many patients have limited opportunities to visit pharmacy organizations in person.

Technological innovations in the healthcare and pharmaceutical industries are enabling patients to learn more about their conditions and take control of their health. New technologies allow doctors to constantly monitor the condition of patients, quickly convey their messages and recommendations to them, as well as give feedback on any side effects when using a particular drug therapy.

Mobile technologies, social networks and other forms of digital marketing already allow pharmacy organizations and manufacturers of pharmaceutical and medical products to use a personalized approach to communicate and exchange information with end consumers, and with the improvement of the regulatory legal framework expected by the professional community in the future, full personalization of pharmaceutical products will be possible. care without distinction between offline and online interactions with the patient.

The market of medicines in our country is of great social importance as well as its economic functions. Providing the population with access to necessary medicines is an integral part of the health care system. In this regard, improving the distribution network of medicines and medical supplies is one of the most urgent problems of today. In solving this problem, the issue of applying and improving marketing methods in drug sales has become a necessary condition for these market subjects.

As a result of the conducted research, we developed a number of recommendations for the distribution and promotion of sales at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC, and their content is as follows:

1. In order to increase the position of "BIOCOSMIC" LLC in the market, it is necessary to develop methods of quick and objective determination of customer needs, because in the current system, receiving orders once a month does not meet the requirements of the times.

2. In order to be superior to competitors, it is desirable to introduce differentiation of orders for medicines, that is, separation by classifications. In particular, grouping drug products by order size and repeat order is one way to meet customer needs.

3. Including forecasting and monitoring the demand for medicinal products We offer as one of the ways to improve sales at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC.

4. It is necessary to further improve the system of incentives for buyers. For this, it is recommended to study foreign and local experience. Another goal of "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is to train and improve the skills of personnel in marketing methods.

5. Since e-commerce has a very small contribution to the turnover of "BIOCOSMIC" LLC today, one of our recommendations is to develop network marketing and e-commerce.

6. Due to the fact that "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is a young, newly formed enterprise, it is necessary to pay more attention to the development of marketing strategy.

The implementation of these recommendations will serve to improve the distribution system of medicines at "BIOCOSMIC" LLC.

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